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Renewable Energy: Alcohol based hybrid biofuel from used cooking oil (UCO) fueled in a CI engine

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Introduction: Biofuels lays positive impact upon economy the environment (1). Hybrid Biofuel is also one of the types of biofuels which contains many advantages *viz.* easy production, economical, 100% possible replacement, no pretreatment and environment friendly (3). The present research is focused upon the effects of hybrid biofuel consists of used cooking oil (UCOHBF), ethanol (viscosity modifier) and 2-butanol (surfactant) on CI engine and also compared its effects with biodiesel blends and petrodiesel.

Methods: The UCOHBF from UCO: ethanol: 2-butanol was 55:28:17, obtained through titration (1,2).

Results & Discussions: Fig. 1 (a) had shown that the brake specific fuel consumption (BSFC) for UCOHBF shows slightly higher trend to those of petrodiesel and biodiesel blends at part and full engine load. This was due to higher density, viscosity and lower GCV of UCOHBF. Fig. 1(b) had shown that the brake thermal efficiency (BTE) for UCOHBF was found slightly lower than UCOB50 and UCOB100 for all load conditions which could be attributed due to low gross calorific value of UCOHBF also the presence of 45% alcohol in UCOHBF. Fig. 1 (c) had shown that the cylinder pressure for UCOHBF follow the same pressure trend to that of petrodiesel and other test blends under all load conditions.

Fig. 1 (a-c): Performance and combustion analysis of hybrid biofuel.

Conclusions: The BSEC and BTE are slightly comparable with B100 and lower with petrodiesel. The combustion characteristics of UCOHBF show higher value among other test blends.

Keywords: Hybrid biofuel, Engine performance, Combustion analysis, CI Engine, emulsion

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